

Problems facing university students during Corona pandemic

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Jul 13, 2022

Revised Sep 26, 2023

Accepted Oct 13, 2023

Keywords:

Corona pandemic

Higher education

Problems

University student's problems

ABSTRACT

University students face many problems and difficulties that hinder their academic and scientific careers. The researchers, in various locations, seek to find solutions to them, especially in light of the global pandemic of Corona, which has exacerbated these problems. Therefore, this study aimed to identify the problems facing university students at Al-Balqa Applied University in Jordan during the Corona pandemic from their viewpoints. Also, this study aimed to identify the relationship between these problems and some variables, such as gender, type of major and academic degree. The researcher used the descriptive approach and developed a questionnaire. The study sample comprised 700 male and female students in the second semester of the academic year 2021/2022. The study concluded that the students' levels of problems got a high degree in all domains and on the instrument as a whole. Besides, there were statistically significant differences following the gender variable in favor of males. The study concluded that there were statistically significant differences following the type of academic major variable and in favor of students of scientific majors. There were no statistically significant differences due to the student's academic degree variable (intermediate diploma, bachelor's degree).

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1. INTRODUCTION

Every society comprises different sectors of children, youth, and old people, and there are distinct sects such as manufacturers, farmers, merchants, scholars, and politicians. A healthy society knows how to fit these sectors. Sects define their duties and respect their rights, and create from them an integrated unit, which are the homeland and the nation. Therefore, young people suffer from different problems due to the differences in these societies, their methods of raising their children, and the values they believe in. Therefore, the youth stage is characterized by the presence of many pressures and hardships that the members of this stage are exposed to, which makes them suffer many problems [1], [2].

The problems facing university students play a major role in influencing their compatibility, academic progress, and achieving their aspirations in the educational and daily fields. These problems will not go away without treatment. They are not just an inevitable psychological crisis of a certain life stage, to be overcome by just skipping this stage. It is a manifestation of the eternal conflict between generations that must be intensified and ended [3]–[5]. The youth stage is a dangerous stage of the life cycle for many reasons: the breadth of the transformations that take place in it, the depth of its impact on the self, and its relationship to others and reality. Hence, it is the stage that requires the greatest amount of reorganization of relations between individuals and others in life, including parents, brothers, friends, and educators. However,

what happens is, to a large extent, the opposite. Organization at this stage is usually more complex and less fluid than it was in childhood. Regarding the relationship with the parents, the young people's emotional and material demands are new, unfamiliar, and more complex than what they are used to, which is more expensive. Therefore, the parents consider them less logical or legitimate. Some parents when they insist on dealing with young people with the same logic and methods that they used to be treated with [3], [6], [7].

Young people go through different types of crises, and some parents refuse to listen to them and share their concerns. Some parents may blame young people for their way of dealing with their problems, thereby generating a deep rift within the young people. It is critical to constantly strive to boost young people's self-esteem, but this must be done without giving them illusions about themselves that may lead to arrogance and condescension toward others. This also has a great negative impact [8]–[11]. Youth problems may arise from the great physical changes that occur to them. They may also arise from the new intertwined situations. Some problems also arise from achieving sexual maturity, and from the restrictions imposed by religion and morals on satisfying this motive.

It is natural that the economic situation is reflected in the psychology of young people and leads to many problems [12], [13]. Several researchers [14]–[17] listed a set of steps on how to deal with the problems faced by young people, such as: i) Defining the problem precisely and all the circumstances that accompanied it or that led to its occurrence is of great importance in determining the easiest way to solve it; ii) Dividing the problem into main elements, because no one can deal with the problem as a single block, but rather as parts. Each part has its own nature, strength, importance, and timing for dealing with it; iii) Searching for proposed solutions, which must be realistic and applicable. Also, they must be decisive, final, not superficial or temporary; formulate these solutions calmly and carefully; iv) Determining the method of implementation that is compatible with each part or element and detail of the solution; and v) Considering the accuracy of the implementation process and not overlooking or ignoring any aspect.

Young people may not find a space in which to express how they feel, or they may lack real communication channels through which they announce and identify their problems. The reason for this is to seek safety and preserve the position that young people create for themselves. Listening to complaints and problems may not be acceptable to some, or some see the necessity of adhering to saying well and praising everything. Otherwise, silence is better than the complaining expression that may injure everyone who has responsibility and a relationship with the youth [6], [7], [10], [12].

The problem of the current study is determined by identifying the problems of university students at Al-Balqa Applied University in Jordan as seen by the students themselves. The problems of university students have been the subject of many studies. A study by Salim [18] aimed to identify the most important psychological problems among university students in light of some variables. The study sample comprised 566 students, on whom a questionnaire was prepared by the researcher. The study concluded that students suffer from psychological disorders significantly, the most important of which are: feelings of frustration, psychological tension, anxiety, fear, and a lack of security. There are differences in the variables of gender, college, and student residence.

Al-Tarrah [19] conducted a study to identify the nature of the personal and societal problems of Kuwaiti youth and identify the differences between them following gender. The sample comprised 1,794 male and female students. The researcher applied to them a questionnaire that he prepared. The results revealed the presence of several problems that young people consider the most important. These problems exemplify not investing their free time effectively; going through periods of sadness and boredom, feeling anxious, and having irrational thoughts control them. Young people's weak abilities to express their desires, feeling the absence of social justice, and feeling marginalized are other examples.

Al-Banna and Al-Rubai [20] conducted a study to identify the problems of Al-Aqsa University students and the differences following variables. The study sample comprised 200 male and female students. A questionnaire, prepared by the researchers, was applied to them. The study results showed that the order of problems was: i) Problems of life and university buildings; ii) Problems of education; iii) Psychological problems; iii) Moral and social problems; and iv) Finally sexual problems. The results also indicated the presence of gender variable in all domains in favor of males, except for educational problems, in which the difference was in favor of females. Also, there were differences due to the social status variable in favor of singles, and there were no differences for the academic major variable.

Ali [21] conducted a study to identify the most important problems facing educational rehabilitation students in light of some variables. The sample comprised 150 male and female students. The researcher applied to them a questionnaire that he prepared. The study concluded that the order of problems is educational problems, organizational administrative problems, psychological problems, economic problems, social problems, and political problems. The results also indicated that there are differences in economic problems between males and females in favor of males, and between delegates and non-delegates in favor of non-delegates.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Study question

Young people play an important role in the process of modernizing their country. The reform claims, from the beginning of the nineteenth century until now, have been carried out by the efforts of young people. They have achieved success due to several factors: their sacrifices, traveling to Europe, meeting with European experts who were brought in by their country from the European experts who were the elite of modernization. The national independence movements against colonialism represented fierce wars; some of which lasted for many years. They were youth movements in their goals and composition to a large extent. The history of the Arab region is full of evidence that the younger generation was at the forefront of the revolutionaries against dependence. They defined their goals, crystallized their slogans, and developed their strategies. They provided its leaders and workforce, paid the largest part of its human cost, and patiently endured a lot of suffering for its success [3], [22]–[25].

The youth stage is that is characterized by the ability to grow in various physical, social, psychological, and mental aspects. Also, it is the ability to innovate and actively participate in bringing about change in the society, in which they live, and developing it. Young people are the pillars of the nation and its foundations upon which it is built. If they reconcile the whole building, and if they are corrupted or their values are shaken, the construction is weak. Therefore, youth issues are among the most important issues of interest to societies striving for progress and prosperity [26], [27].

Since young people constitute a large proportion of society, it is worthwhile to study the problems they face; especially if we know that psychologists almost unanimously agree that the phenomenon/stage of youth represents one of the core hubs of modern psychological research. This is due to the characteristics and components of the previous and later stages that this stage bears [28]–[31]. Moreover, higher educational institutions in any country represent the top of the educational system. Educational institutions have great importance as they form society members to carry out the high professional jobs required by society. They contribute to its development through their intellectual and scientific influences. One of the most important goals of higher education is the optimal preparation of the manpower needed to work in all the disciplines needed by society [20]. Thus, it represents a quality of education that differs from the regular pattern in public educational schools regarding the nature of study and patterns of social interaction. This helps the students' personalities grow, enhances their abilities to learn, think, make decisions, and take responsibility. Thus, students must adapt to the university environment [31]–[35].

Young people are facing an unclear and unknown future, due to the conditions that the entire world is experiencing at present, represented by the spread of the coronavirus; especially after educational institutions suddenly are forced to switch to distance learning to ensure the continuity of the teaching and learning process. Educational institutions use the Internet, smartphones, and computers to communicate remotely with students [34]. The current study attempts to identify the most prominent problems facing university students in order to help the experts communicate with adolescents and youth to appropriately solve these problems. This study aims to overcome these problems and achieve the normal growth of adolescents' and young people's personalities.

The importance of recognizing these problems is not evidenced by the numerous studies that have dealt with this topic. However, these studies' significance lies in investigating these problems and developing appropriate solutions to them [34], [36], [37]; Other studies include [18]–[21], [27], [28], [38]–[40]. Thus, this study seeks to answer the following questions: i) What are the problems facing university students at Al-Balqa Applied University during the Corona pandemic from their viewpoints? ii) Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) in the problems faced by Al-Balqa Applied University students during the Corona pandemic from their viewpoints? Are they attributed to the gender variable (males, females)? iii) Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) in the problems faced by Al-Balqa Applied University students during the Corona pandemic from their viewpoints? Are they attributed to the student's academic major type variable (scientific, humanitarian)? and iv) Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) in the problems faced by Al-Balqa Applied University students during the Corona pandemic from their viewpoints? Are they attributed to the student's academic degree variable (intermediate diploma, bachelor's degree)?

2.2. Study significance

The importance of the current study is reflected in: i) The importance of the issue of university students and the problems they face, especially in light of the global Corona pandemic; ii) Adolescence and youth are important as they are the most important stages of human development; iii) The importance of university life and the new horizons it opens up for the individual; iv) The importance of higher educational institutions and their great role in developing students' personalities and preparing them for practical life in various respects; v) The importance of detecting and addressing the problems facing adolescents and youth

and trying to develop appropriate solutions for them to achieve benefits from young people's energies and potential; vi) Conducting studies that reflect the university students' interest in these problems, finding solutions to them, and developing their motivations towards learning and the university as a whole; and vii) Conducting such studies gives the university and its faculty and administrative staff a perception of the problems facing university students.

2.3. Study limitations

The current study is limited to students who are currently enrolled in studies and are actually registered at Al-Balqa Applied University in Jordan, with its various colleges extending from north to south, and its various specializations, whether scientific or humanities, and its various academic degrees, whether intermediate diploma, bachelor's, for the academic year (2021/2022 AD).

2.4. Study objectives

The study aims to identify: i) The problems faced by Al-Balqa Applied University students during the Corona pandemic from their viewpoints; and ii) Whether there are statistically significant differences in the problems facing university students, attributed to the variables: Gender (males, females), type of academic major (scientific, humanitarian), and the student's academic degree (intermediate diploma, bachelor's).

2.5. Terms and procedural definitions

2.5.1. Problems

Dahab and Albadri [41] believed that the problems are an obstacle to satisfying our needs or an ambiguous situation for which we do not find a specific explanation. Greenberg, London, and McKay [42] defined them as the difficulties or conditions that are not desired by most members of society; because they prevent the individual or society from adequately satisfying needs and achieving goals, leading to direct harm to one or both of them, now or in the future. Hejazy [3] defined it as a state of dissatisfaction or an undesirable result, and the feeling of the presence of obstacles that must be overcome to achieve a goal, and it arises from the presence of several known or unknown reasons. Al-Tarrah [19] defined it as an exciting situation to which an individual is exposed, to which he had not previously been exposed, and therefore he does not have a ready response to it.

2.5.2. University students

Al-Mukhambetova and Hernández-Torrano [43] defined them as that group of society who pursue their education after obtaining a secondary or preparatory certificate, and their ages range from 18-23 years. Ali [21] defined it as the period of life in which young people join the university and are between 17 and 25 years old. It is characterized by strength, activity, and the ability to work, achieve, create, and accept new ideas. It is characterized by extreme sensitivity to new situations and confronting reality and its problems. It is considered a stage of testing and planning for the future, but it lacks for experience and experience, and this period requires preparation and qualification to.

2.5.3. Corona virus

It is a family of viruses that may cause illness in animals and humans [41]. It causes respiratory diseases in humans ranging in severity from common colds to more severe diseases such as Middle East Respiratory Syndrome, and severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS). It is characterized by a rapid spread. Salim [18] defined it as an infectious disease caused by the latest virus discovered from the coronavirus strain that causes severe acute respiratory syndrome and which is transmitted through direct contact with the patient through droplets coming from the nose or mouth.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

The descriptive approach was used because it is the most appropriate approach to the nature of the study problem and its objectives. The study population comprises 45,000 students of Al-Balqa Applied University who are enrolled in all its faculties, majors, and various educational programs. The sample comprised 700 male and female students from Al-Balqa Applied University from various faculties, majors, and academic degrees as shown in Table 1.

To achieve the study objectives, the researcher reviewed the literature and previous studies related to the subject of this current study [18], [19], [44]. A questionnaire was developed, comprising in its initial form 39 items distributed in three domains equally. The first domain is academic problems, and it includes 13 items. The second domain is social and family problems, and it includes 13 items. The third domain is psychological problems, and it includes 13 items.

Table 1. The study variables

Variable	Categories	Number	Percentage
Gender	Male	421	60%
	Female	279	40%
Student's type of academic	Scientific	221	32%
Major	Humanitarian	479	68%
Student's academic degree	Bachelor's	298	43%
	Intermediate diploma's	402	57%
Total		700	100%

3.1. Study instrument's validity

The validity of the tool measure what is intended to be measured [20] or measuring the validity of the research tool in achieving the objectives of the study, which leads to a high level of confidence in the results reached by the researcher that can be generalized [41]. It is the validity of the tool to measure what it was designed to measure and its validity in measuring the trait or traits that the researcher wants to measure [12]. The validity of the current study instrument has been confirmed through the following:

3.1.1. The referees' validity (apparent validity)

This was done by presenting the questionnaire in its initial form to 12 experts and referees. They have expertise and competence in curricula, teaching, social service, measurement, and evaluation from Al-Balqa Applied, Yarmouk, and Jordan universities. It is to obtain their views and observations regarding adding, modifying, or deleting items from the scale. The referees recommended a set of changes that enhanced the questionnaire. Some modifications were made to some items on the scale, such as merging, deleting, and modifying some items based on the referees' opinions. The scale comprises 31 items in its final exam, distributed over the anaphoric study domains.

3.1.2. The validity of the internal consistency

After verifying the referees' (virtual) validity of the instrument, the questionnaire was applied to a random exploratory sample from the same study community, but outside its sample. This sample was from the Al-Balqa Applied University students, comprising 60 male and female students. The validity of the internal consistency was used to calculate the correlation coefficients between each of the scale items and the total scores of the scale.

Table 2 shows the correlation coefficients between each of the scale items and the total sum of the items. It shows that the indicated correlation coefficients are statistically significant. Thus, the scale items are considered valid and measure what they were designed to measure.

Table 2. Correlation coefficients between statement and its domain and the domains for the scale as a whole

First domain: Academic problems		Second domain: Social and family problems		Third domain: Psychological problems	
Statement	Correlation coefficient	Statement	Correlation coefficient	Statement	Correlation coefficient
1	0.584	1	0.574	1	0.594
2	0.597	2	0.597	2	0.534
3	0.582	3	0.584	3	0.562
4	0.531	4	0.502	4	0.597
5	0.584	5	0.534	5	0.551
6	0.552	6	0.594	6	0.564
7	0.594	7	0.550	7	0.508
10	0.508	10	0.531		
		11	0.597		
		12	0.584		
		12	0.502		
		14	0.531		
Domains as a whole		First domain	0.523		
		Second domain	0.584		
		Third domain	0.523		

3.2. Study instrument reliability

The reliability of the test or instrument is approximately given by the same scale of results if it is re-applied to the same respondents after a certain period [45]. It also means stability, meaning that if the measurement processes are repeated on a single individual, his score shows some stability [12]. It also means objectivity in the sense that the individual obtains the same score, regardless of the differences between the researcher who applies the test or who corrects it. In this case, the fixed test is a test in which the individual is

estimated with an estimate that no two people differ in its calculation [16]. It also means that the results shown by the tool are stable, meaning that they indicate the same results if they were re-applied to the same sample under the same conditions after an appropriate period of time [21].

3.2.1. Reliability using the internal homogeneity method (Cronbach's alpha coefficient)

The internal consistency of reliability coefficient was calculated using Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the degrees of the instrument as a whole and the sub-domains of the instrument. The internal consistency coefficient for the instrument degrees was 0.87. The internal consistency coefficient for the instrument ranged from 0.81 to 0.92 and those values were statistically significant.

3.2.2. Reliability by repetition

The indicators of the instrument reliability were calculated by applying the instrument to 30 male and female students (experimental sample) and re-applying the instrument at an interval of two weeks. The Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated between the two applications of the instrument as a whole and for all the sub- instrument domains. The reliability coefficient of the recurrence method for the instrument's degrees as a whole was 0.80. The correlation coefficients between the two applications for the instrument's domains ranged from 0.77 to 0.84 and all of those values were statistically significant as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Pearson correlation with repetition and Cronbach's alpha on the fields of study

Domain	Items number	Cronbach's alpha coefficient	Pearson's correlation coefficient of repetition
Academic problems	10	*0.88	*0.84
Social and family problems	14	*0.81	*0.71
Psychological Problems	7	*0.92	*0.77
Problems as a whole	31	*0.87	*0.80

*A function at the ($\alpha=0.01$) significance level

3.3. Study instrument correction

The students' answers to the instrument items were distributed following the 5-point Likert scale as: (strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, strongly disagree), and grades (1, 2, 3, 4, 5) were given respectively to the negative items. However, the degrees (5, 4, 3, 2, 1) were given, respectively, to the positive items. Thus, the lowest score obtained by the study respondent is 40; and the highest score obtained by the study respondent is 200. The answers' degrees ranged between (1-5) degrees and the problems in this study were divided into three categories (high problems, average problems, and low problems). The highest degree of the item, which is 5, was divided by 3, which are the categories of problems, and the result was 1.33. This number was adopted as the length of the category that determines the direction, and thus the length of the direction category is: i) Low problems ranged from 1 to 2.33; ii) Average problems ranged from 2.33 to 3.67; and iii) High problems ranged from 3.68 to 5.

3.4. Statistical methods used

In order to achieve the objectives of the study and answer its questions, the necessary statistical treatment was carried out, which was represented by the use of a group of methods that contribute to achieving the objectives of the study, which were represented by the Pearson correlation coefficient to extract the reliability coefficient of the questionnaire. Arithmetic means and standard deviations were also used, in addition to using a t-test for differences between two independent groups.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First, the results related to the first question "What are the problems facing university students at Al-Balqa Applied University during the Corona pandemic from their viewpoints?" Answering this question, the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the respondents' responses were extracted from the university student's problems scale as a whole, and for each study domain. They were shown in Table 4 to Table 7, respectively. Table 4 shows the problems of university students in the academic problems domain.

Table 4 shows that eight items obtained a high degree, and two items had an average degree. The arithmetic means of the items in the academic problems domain ranged from 3.52 to 4.38. The arithmetic means for the domain as a whole was 3.96, with a standard deviation of 0.58, and with a high degree. It is noted that there is a negative view of the courses, especially those focusing on memorization. This is one of the major issues confronting the educational system at various stages. However, university education, as it is a type of advanced education, should aim to focus on other cognitive goals, such as understanding, application, analysis, installation, and evaluation. It is to raise a generation capable of change. Most of the

majors in universities are humanitarian and social majors. There are lot of memorizations in their courses, unlike some medical or engineering majors, which are characterized by their practical aspect. Students are concerned about the problem of their enrollment in their faculties and majors, which is based on their high school averages, not on desires and ambitions. This issue arises in Jordanian universities' unified admission system. It depends mainly on the average without taking into account the student's desire, inclination, or ambition for a particular major. It is because students' averages will determine their colleges' admission. Also, most or all of these colleges may not meet students' desires. There is another problem facing students who, have been accepted into a particular college and will use their averages again in determining the department they will join. Through the researchers' work as instructors in the various academic departments, they found this result: a large portion of the students did not enroll in their university, colleges, departments, and majors as per their desires.

The lack of attention to individuals' differences among students is one of the important problems in the psychology domain. Not taking these differences into account is a big problem. Thus, faculty members at all levels of education should give individual differences the attention they deserve, so students' optimal use of their energies and abilities will be achieved. The students' views of academic courses, as not meeting their ambitions, may be due to the old curricula, distance from practical life, and some weak basic vocabulary.

Table 4. Arithmetic means and standard deviations for the field of academic problems

Rank	Items	Arithmetic means	Standard deviations	Degree
1	Teaching focuses on memorization and neglects other important aspects	4.38	0.58	High
2	Enrolling in college because of the average, not the desire	4.30	0.62	High
3	Lack of attention to individual differences among students	4.21	0.54	High
4	The academic courses do not meet students' ambition	4.12	0.72	High
5	Low academic achievement	4.08	0.63	High
6	Difficulty of exams	3.92	0.69	High
7	Instructors' unfair treatment of students	3.82	0.50	High
8	Students' lack of knowledge of effective study strategies	3.71	0.52	High
9	Students' weak motivation to learn	3.63	0.57	Average
10	The multiplicity of laws on campus	3.52	0.51	Average
	The total degree for the academic problems domain as a whole	3.96	0.58	High

Table 5 shows that 11 items obtained a high degree and three items had an average degree. The arithmetic means of the items in the social and family problems domain ranged from 3.47 to 4.78. The arithmetic mean of the domain as a whole was 4.05, with a standard deviation of 0.62, and to a high degree. It is noted that the unemployment problem ranked first. This problem is considered a major problem facing Jordanian youth, Arab youth, and global youth. The reason for this may be the large number of graduates from universities in different disciplines, especially the humanitarian disciplines, whose graduates do not find a job opportunity easily compared to some graduates from some other scientific disciplines such as medical specializations. Working in places far from the place of residence and the problem of unemployment are considered the biggest social problems facing the youth group. Also, the problem of forming relationships with the opposite gender is considered to be a big problem. It is due to the nature of customs and traditions that prevent a young man or girl from being associated with another without a legal link between them.

This problem is linked to another social problem, which is the high cost of dowries and the complexity of marriage [44], [45]. Marriage for young people has become a problem that requires a solution and assistance [28]. Marriage has become a problem due to the complexity of its financial requirements. This problem may be common to both genders in some societies that place financial requirements on both males and females. However, the problem is almost clear to males more than females because the requirements for marriage fall on the shoulders of males only. The marital future becomes a key problem because of the fear of delaying the marriage age and the lack of information and skills to form an independent family. Another reason is fear of the lack of money. It is money that secures the future for young people.

The problem of neglecting authentic customs and traditions is one of the problems facing university students following their answers. This problem is related to society, and young people are sensitive to it, considering that young people are afraid of the tremendous pressure on them to strive to achieve and provide material needs on values, assets, and social norms. This may be because many young members of society have abandoned the customs and traditions instilled in them. The problem of parents imposing on their sons the type of university or major that they should pursue may be to achieve a dream that the parents fail to fulfill; or because the college is far from the place of residence, so the parents want to save money. Society's view of the type of college and major plays a greater role for parents than it does for children. This leads the parents to push the children to study at a particular college, despite their unwillingness to do so.

Parents' interference in choosing friends for their sons may be the reason for their fear of their children being drawn into bad friendships and affecting them negatively. This gives us a positive, optimistic view that parents insist and seek for their children to complete university studies despite the financial hardships faced by families. However, in some cases, some students may have a determination not to complete university studies due to the difficult financial circumstances of the family. Also, some parents provide an additional source of income from their sons' work. Some students support their families when there is no other financial source. This may stem from the parents' lack of knowledge of the importance of completing their sons' studies and obtaining university certificates. Other reason is parents' negative attitudes towards females' education and their refusal of their daughters' mixture with males.

Table 5. Arithmetic means and standard deviations for the field of social and family problems

Rank	Items	Arithmetic means	Standard deviations	Degree
1	Unemployment spread	4.78	0.69	High
2	Difficulty forming relationships with the opposite gender	4.65	0.78	High
3	High dowries and the complexity of marriage	4.43	0.70	High
4	It is difficult to abide by the norms prevailing in society	4.36	0.63	High
5	Fear of being unmarried (spinsterhood)	4.29	0.58	High
6	Neglecting the original customs and traditions	4.14	0.52	High
7	Tribal and sectarian fanaticism	4.01	0.54	High
8	Parents impose on their children the university or major	3.90	0.61	High
9	Parents' involvement in choosing their children's friends	3.88	0.73	High
10	The multiplicity of disagreements within the family	3.82	0.65	High
11	Parents' bad treatment of their children	3.77	0.58	High
12	Parents' poor attention to their children	3.63	0.53	Average
13	Society's negative view of mixing at the university	3.58	0.54	Average
14	Parents' insistence not to complete the study	3.47	0.71	Average
	The total degree for the social and family problems	4.05	0.62	High

Table 6 shows that four items got a high degree and three items got an average degree. The arithmetic means of the items in the psychological problems domain ranged from 3.44 to 4.29. The arithmetic mean of the domain as a whole was 3.82 with a standard deviation of 0.60, and to a high degree. This result is attributed to the fact that university students feel anxious when thinking about the future. This problem may be one of the general problems that all individuals face. However, it is most prevalent among young people due to rapid social and economic change, massive population growth, and an increase in the number of graduate students. Also, the shortcomings in planning exist, and the balance between the number of graduates and the needs of the labor market does not exist. The expected problems that may result from this are directly or indirectly responsible for the prevalence of psychological future anxiety among university students. This idea is consistent with the results of studies [4], [7].

Also, hesitation in making decisions related to the special problems of university students is a big and important problem, and this problem is related to many other psychological problems. The hesitation may be a result of constant fear of the future. It may be due to a lack of confidence, reliance on others and their advice, or advice directed at young people. Thus, everyone who has a relationship with young people should try to enhance their ability to make appropriate decisions for everything they face.

The presence of frustration among university youth may be due to several reasons, including preventing the individuals from reaching their goals, the conflict between goals and social and legislative laws. The failure to achieve an expected academic level, exams, and the accompanying psychological, economic, and emotional problems exemplify other reasons. The conflict between their values and their friends' ones is evaluated.

Table 6. Arithmetic means and standard deviations for the field of psychological problems

Rank	Items	Arithmetic means	Standard deviations	Degree
1	Feeling anxious when thinking about the future	4.29	0.61	High
2	Fear of failure in study and life	4.18	0.58	High
3	Reluctance to make decisions about own problems	3.98	0.63	High
4	Low self-confidence	3.74	0.70	High
5	Difficulty concentrating attention	3.61	0.55	Average
6	Feeling frustrated	3.53	0.53	Average
7	Feeling alienated on campus	3.44	0.62	Average
	The total degree for the psychological problems domain	3.82	0.60	High

Table 7 indicates that the level of university students' problems at Al-Balqa Applied University on the domains and instruments as a whole was high. The arithmetic mean of the study sample's degrees on the instrument as a whole was 3.94, with a standard deviation 0.60. The table also indicates that the arithmetic means of the study domains ranged from 3.82 to 4.05. The highest arithmetic mean for the social and family problems domain was 4.05 and a standard deviation 0.62; the lowest arithmetic mean for the psychological problems domain was 3.82 and a standard deviation 0.60. In general, these means indicate a high level of problems for university students.

Table 7. Arithmetic means and standard deviations of students' scores on the study tool

Domain	Arithmetic means	Standard deviations	Level
Social and family problems	4.05	0.62	High
Academic problems	3.96	0.58	High
Psychological problems	3.82	0.60	High
Problems as a whole	3.94	0.60	High

Second, the results related to the second question "Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) regarding problems facing university youth at Al-Balqa Applied University during the Corona pandemic from their viewpoints? Are these differences explained by gender variable (males or females)?" Table 8 indicates there are apparent differences between the average degrees of students on the study instrument as a whole, and on each of the sub-domains of the instrument. These differences followed the gender variable (males, females); and to find out whether there are statistically significant differences in the impact of gender on the problems of university students. The T-test was used to examine these differences as shown in Table 8. It is noted that there are statistically significant differences in the problems of university students. It is attributed to the student's gender variable (males, females), on the study problems domain and in favor of males. The calculated (T) value reached 0.965 at the level of significance 0.088. There were no statistically significant differences regarding the university students' problems in the social and family problems and the psychological problems domains and on the instrument as a whole.

This result can be attributed to the similarity concerning students' social, family, and psychological problems they face. This result is due to the personal circumstances and the similarity of the social and family environment in which the students live. The two researchers believe that there are similarities and convergence in educational experiences and curricular and extracurricular activities between males and females; which worked to reduce the differences in the level of problems facing university students for both genders. There were differences in the academic domain, to be for males' interest. The reason for this is that university students, especially males, engage in work other than studying to secure the costs university studies, such as books, transportation, and other expenses. This contributes to the aggravation of their academic crisis, unlike female students who spend most of their time at home and work. Thus, they have plenty of time to complete the required studies. This idea is consistent with the results of studies [4], [45].

Table 8. Arithmetic means and standard deviations of students' scores on the study tool based on gender

Domain	Gender	Arithmetic means	Standard deviations	Calculated "T" value	Freedom degrees	Significance level
Academic problems	Males	4.77	0.59	0.965	87	0.088
	Females	4.25	0.62			
Social and family problems	Males	4.86	0.63	0.854	87	0.064
	Females	4.79	0.58			
Psychological problems	Males	4.15	0.64	0.664	87	0.059
	Females	4.26	0.59			
Domains as a whole	Males	4.59	0.62	0.664	87	0.264
	Females	4.43	0.59			

Third, the results related to the second question "Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) regarding problems facing university students at Al-Balqa Applied University during the Corona pandemic from their viewpoints?" Are these differences attributed to the student's academic major (humanitarian, scientific) variable? Table 9 indicates that there are apparent differences between the average scores of students on the study instrument as a whole, and on each of the sub-domains of the instrument. These differences followed the variable of the student's academic major type (humanitarian, scientific) and to verify the impact of academic major type on the problems of university students, the T-Test was used to examine these differences. It is noted that there are statistically significant differences in the

problems of university students. It is attributed to students' academic major type (humanitarian, scientific), on the academic problems domain, and for the benefit of scientific- major students. The calculated (T) value reached 0.887 at the level of significance 0.067 for the psychological problems domain to be in favor of scientific- discipline domains. The calculated (T) value reached 0.964 at the level of significance 0.084. However, there were no statistically significant differences in the problems of university students in the social and family problems domain and across the instrument as a whole. This result can be attributed to the fact that scientific- discipline students feel the pressure, importance, and necessity of studying. Students in the humanities, on the other hand, feel less pressure to succeed in their studies. Also, scientific disciplines such as medical, engineering, and others need long study hours. All of this contributes to the increase of students' problems, exacerbating their psychological problems due to their integration into study for long periods to obtain high academic grades. This idea is consistent with the results of studies [1], [13].

Fourth, the results related to the third question, Table 10 indicates that there are no apparent differences between the students' average degrees on the study instrument as a whole, and on each of the sub- instrument domains. These differences followed the student's academic degree (intermediate diploma, bachelor's degree) variable; and to verify the impact of the students' academic degrees on their problems, the T-test was used to examine these differences. It is noted that there are no statistically significant differences in the problems facing university students. These differences are attributed to the student's academic degree (intermediate diploma, bachelor's degree) variable, in all study domains and on the instrument as a whole. This result can be attributed to the fact that students, regardless of their academic level, face scholastic, social, family, and psychological problems in a close manner. This is because the study patterns and plans are similar among students. Also, the instructors who teach diploma students are often the same instructors who teach bachelor's students, and this leads to similar stereotypes among students. The similarity in the degree system between the diploma and the bachelor's degree also contributes to the problems facing university students in general. This idea is consistent with the results of studies [39], [43].

Table 9. Arithmetic means and standard deviations of students' scores on the study tool according to the variable of specialization type

Domain	Major	Arithmetic means	Standard deviations	Calculated "T" value	Freedom degrees	Significance level
Academic problems	Humanitarian	3.98	0.74	0.887	74	0.067
	Scientific	4.64	0.77			
Social and family problems	Humanitarian	4.45	0.69	0.657	74	0.097
	Scientific	4.58	0.62			
Psychological problems	Humanitarian	3.76	0.54	0.964	74	0.084
	Scientific	4.33	0.75			
Domains as a whole	Humanitarian	4.06	0.65	2.854	74	0.264
	Scientific	4.51	0.71			

Table 10. Arithmetic means and standard deviations of students' grades on the study tool according to the student's academic grade variable

Domain	Academic degree	Arithmetic means	Standard deviations	Calculated "T" value	freedom degrees	significance level
Academic problems	Intermediate diploma	3.77	0.52	0.558	72	0.063
	Bachelor	4.06	0.63			
Social and family problems	Intermediate diploma	3.69	0.50	0.602	72	0.077
	Bachelor	3.73	0.59			
Psychological problems	Intermediate diploma	3.83	0.64	0.741	72	0.072
	Bachelor	3.96	0.66			
Domains as a whole	Intermediate diploma	3.76	0.55	2.663	72	0.224
	Bachelor	3.91	0.62			

5. CONCLUSION

The study found that university students suffer from many academic problems, including low academic achievement and college enrollment because of the average, not the desire and difficulty of exams. In addition, university students suffer from many social and family problems, including rampant unemployment, high dowries, complicated marriages, neglect of authentic customs and traditions, and tribal and sectarian intolerance. University students are also exposed to many psychological problems, including fear of failing in school and life, feeling anxious thinking about the future, difficulty in focusing attention.

The results concluded that there are statistically significant differences in the problems facing university students due to the gender and the variable of the type of academic specialization. In addition, there are no statistically significant differences in the problems facing university students due to the student's

academic degree variable. The researchers recommend intensifying attention to young people, as they are half of the present and all of the future, in addition to holding introductory seminars for university students related to training them on the best ways to deal with the problems they face in various aspects. It is also necessary to strengthen the role of educational and psychological counseling within higher education institutions to play its role in assisting university students in overcoming the problems that stand in their way. The researchers suggest conducting a study to identify the problems of management and teaching staff in higher education institutions; or to identify the problems of graduate students and conducting a comparative study for university students in different universities or environments.

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